

Developing a Bayes Optimal Prediction Framework for Multilevel Analysis Based on Bayesian Decision Theory

Kohei Horinouchi*

Toshiyasu Matsushima*

Abstract

Multilevel analysis is increasingly valued for its ability to handle complex, hierarchically structured data, especially across diverse research areas. Conventional approaches in multilevel analysis often emphasize model fitting and parameter estimation but overlook the critical aspect of predictive optimality. In this study, we propose a framework designed to enhance prediction accuracy for multilevel data. Based on Bayesian decision theory, our approach enables prediction that guarantees statistical optimality. To analytically derive Bayes optimal predictions, we apply the variational Bayes algorithm to approximate posterior distributions of model parameters. In simulation studies, we confirm the superior predictive accuracy of our proposed method over conventional approaches.

Key Words: Multilevel Analysis, Multilevel Data, Hierarchical Linear Models, Bayesian Decision Theory, Variational Bayes Algorithm

1. Introduction

Multilevel analysis is a statistical technique used to analyze hierarchical data structures, often referred to as multilevel data, where observations are nested within multiple levels, allowing for the estimation of effects at each level (Harvey Goldstein 2010). A classic example in education involves students nested within classrooms and classrooms nested within schools, which can be effectively analyzed as multilevel data (Raudenbush & Bryk 2002). This approach enables researchers to disentangle variation at different levels and simultaneously assess the influence of factors at each level. Furthermore, multilevel analysis has been widely applied in diverse fields such as public health and economics. For instance, it is employed in public health to evaluate the impact of neighborhood-level social factors on individual health outcomes (Diez-Roux 2000). Similarly, in economics, researchers utilize multilevel analysis to investigate how income inequality across regions affects the health status of residents (Subramanian & Kawachi 2004).

In multilevel analysis, data are assumed to be hierarchically structured. To account for the structure, hierarchical linear models (HLMs) or multilevel models are employed, which incorporate both fixed and random effects. Fixed effects represent influences that are constant across all individuals. For example, in education, fixed effects capture the overall impact of instructional time on student achievement. Conversely, random effects represent random variation across classes such as classrooms or schools, reflecting individual-level or class-level deviations (Raudenbush & Bryk 2002). By modeling fixed and random effects concurrently, researchers can distinguish and estimate effects at individual and class levels.

In multilevel analysis, estimating parameters within hierarchical linear models, including fixed effects, variance components of random effects, and residual variance, is crucial. Conventional approaches to parameter estimation in multilevel analysis have predominantly relied on maximum likelihood (ML) and restricted maximum likelihood (REML) estimation (Patterson & Thompson 1971, David A. Harville 1977, Nicholas T. Longford 1987, Searle 1992). Alternatively, Bayesian estimation methods have also been proposed, offering a flexible framework for handling complex data structures (Gelfand et al.

*Department of Applied Mathematics, Waseda University, 3-4-1 Okubo, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo, Japan

1990, Zeger & Karim 1991, Seltzer 1993, Seltzer et al. 1996, Browne et al. 2002, Browne & Draper 2006).

Predicting a target variable for new explanatory variables is a crucial problem in multilevel analysis. Two scenarios exist for such predictions: one where the new explanatory variables belong to a class already present in the existing data, and another where they belong to a new, previously unobserved class (Jiang & Zhang 2002, Jiang 2021). Conventional multilevel analysis predominantly employs parameter estimation-based prediction for both scenarios (Gelman & Hill 2006, Harvey Goldstein 2010), with widespread applications across diverse fields. Examples include predicting clinical events in healthcare (Kim et al. 2021), forecasting election results and voter turnout in social sciences (Vendeville et al. 2021), assessing vacancy risks for detached housing in urban planning (Lee et al. 2022), conducting predictions in education and policy evaluation (Mangino & Finch 2021), and informing decision-making regarding treatment efficacy (Kavelaars et al. 2023). However, the optimality of these conventional methods, rooted in parameter estimation, concerning target variable prediction accuracy needs to be addressed more.

This study focuses on the second of the two prediction scenarios mentioned earlier, where the class to which the new explanatory variables belong is not included in the set of classes observed in the existing data. We assume that both class-level and individual-level explanatory variables are available. In the school and student example, class-level explanatory variables pertain to the school, while individual-level explanatory variables describe the student. We propose a framework for deriving the Bayes optimal prediction under these assumptions and positing a hierarchical linear model relating the target and explanatory variables. This prediction minimizes the Bayes risk function, according to Bayesian decision theory (James O. Berger 1985), for new class-level and individual-level explanatory variables randomly sampled from the population. It is important to note that the prior distributions for the parameters in this study are distinct from conventional approaches, specifically chosen to enable analytical derivation of the predictive distribution.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the probabilistic model relating the target and explanatory variables assumed in conventional multilevel analysis and briefly reviews conventional parameter estimation methods. Section 3 introduces the probabilistic model and prior distributions for the parameters employed in this study and derives the Bayes optimal prediction based on Bayesian decision theory. Section 4 derives a Bayes sub-optimal prediction, approximating the Bayes optimal prediction using variational Bayes methods. Section 5 presents the results of numerical experiments conducted on synthetic data to evaluate the predictive accuracy of the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

This section describes hierarchical linear models and linear mixed models (Raudenbush & Bryk 2002, Harvey Goldstein 2010), which are statistical models assumed in previous research on the multilevel analysis and outlines the primary estimation methods. In multilevel analysis, the population data are assumed to have a hierarchical structure. Therefore, hereafter, let $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$ be the index of a class sampled from the population, and $k_j \in \{1, \dots, n_j\}$ be the index of an individual sampled from class j . Furthermore, in multilevel analysis, it is often assumed that explanatory variables are obtained at both the class level and the individual level. Accordingly, let $w_j \in \mathbb{R}^Q$ be the Q -dimensional vector of explanatory variables for class j , and $x_{jk_j} \in \mathbb{R}^P$ be the P -dimensional vector of explanatory variables for individual k_j belonging to class j , with

the target variable denoted as $y_{jk_j} \in \mathbb{R}$. Additionally, let $\mathbf{X}_j := (\mathbf{x}_{j1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j \times P}$ and $\mathbf{y}_j := (y_{j1}, \dots, y_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j}$. The multilevel data are then represented as $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$, where \mathbf{X}^J , \mathbf{w}^J , and \mathbf{y}^J are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{X}^J := \{\mathbf{X}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{w}^J := \{\mathbf{w}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}^J := \{\mathbf{y}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}. \quad (3)$$

Given class-level and individual-level explanatory variables, the individual-level regression model in a multilevel model is assumed to be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \boldsymbol{\alpha}_j + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \lambda_\varepsilon^{-1} \mathbf{I}_{n_j}). \quad (4)$$

The error term $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j$ in equation (4) is assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean 0 and covariance matrix $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 \mathbf{I}_{n_j}$. Also, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{P+1}$ represents the regression coefficients, which vary for each class j . Here,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{x}_{j1}^\top \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \mathbf{x}_{jn_j}^\top \end{pmatrix} = (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{j1}, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j \times (P+1)}. \quad (5)$$

where P is the number of individual-level explanatory variables. Furthermore, a regression model is assumed for $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j$ in multilevel models. This is called the class-level regression model and is assumed to be expressed using the class-level explanatory variables as:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{u}_j. \quad (6)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1)}$ in equation (6) is called the fixed effect, and $\mathbf{u}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{P+1}$ is called the random effect for class j . \mathbf{u}_j is assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean 0 and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_u$. Here,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1) \times (P+1)(Q+1)}. \quad (7)$$

which represents the class-level explanatory variable matrix, and Q is the number of class-level explanatory variables. Therefore, from equations (4) and (6), combining these yields:

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\beta} + \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \mathbf{u}_j + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j. \quad (8)$$

As discussed in Section 1, this study addresses the prediction problem where the class to which the new explanatory variables belong is not present in the set of classes observed in the existing data. In this scenario, the random effects of the new class cannot be estimated from the known multilevel data. Therefore, by marginalizing out the random effects in equation (8), we obtain the following distribution, where \mathbf{w}_{new} denotes the new class-level explanatory variables, \mathbf{x}_{new} represents the new individual-level explanatory variables, and y_{new} represents the new target variable:

$$y_{\text{new}} \sim \mathcal{N}(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_u \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}). \quad (9)$$

Note that $\mathcal{N}(\cdot \mid \cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the probability density function of the normal distribution.

Conventionally, prediction is performed based on equation (9) after estimating the fixed effects β , the variance-covariance matrix of the random effects Σ_u , and the error variance σ_ε^2 from equation (8). In maximum likelihood estimation and restricted maximum likelihood estimation approaches, β , Σ_u and σ_ε^2 are assumed to be unknown fixed values. Estimation is performed through methods such as the EM algorithm (Dempster et al. 1977), Fisher's scoring algorithm (Nicholas T. Longford 1987), and IGLS (iterative generalized least squares) (Goldstein 1986). On the other hand, in Bayesian approaches, β , Σ_u , and σ_ε^2 are considered random variables and prior distributions are assumed. In this case, conjugate prior distributions such as a normal distribution for β , an inverse gamma distribution for σ_ε^2 , and an inverse Wishart distribution for Σ_u are often assumed. Alternatively, non-informative prior distributions such as Jeffreys prior or uniform distributions may be assumed for each (Seltzer 1993, Seltzer et al. 1996, Gelman & Hill 2006, Harvey Goldstein 2010, Gelman 2013). However, for the variance of the random effect Σ_u , it is sometimes assumed that $\Sigma_u := \text{diag}(\sigma_u^2)$, where $\sigma_u^2 := (\sigma_{u0}^2, \dots, \sigma_{uP}^2)^\top$, and each σ_{up}^2 ($p = 0, 1, \dots, P$) follows an inverse gamma distribution (Gelman & Hill 2006).

3. Proposed Method

In this section, we set prior distributions for parameters and derive a Bayes optimal prediction based on Bayesian decision theory. In our study, for the probabilistic model between the target variable and explanatory variables given in equation (8), we assume the following prior distributions for the fixed effect parameter β , the random effects \mathbf{u}_j ($j = 1, \dots, J$), and the precision of the error term $\lambda_\varepsilon (= \sigma_\varepsilon^{-2})$:

$$\beta \mid \lambda_\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\beta \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_\beta)^{-1}), \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_j \mid \lambda_\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{u}_j \mid \mathbf{0}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_u)^{-1}) \quad (j = 1, \dots, J), \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda_\varepsilon \sim \text{Gam}(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid a_\varepsilon, b_\varepsilon). \quad (12)$$

Here, $\text{Gam}(\cdot \mid \cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the probability density function of the gamma distribution, and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1)}$, $\mathbf{K}_\beta^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1) \times (P+1)(Q+1)}$, and $\mathbf{K}_u^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1) \times (P+1)}$ are assumed to be known constants. Notably, the prior distributions for β and \mathbf{u}_j ($j = 1, \dots, J$) are conditioned on λ_ε . Based on this prior distribution assumption, the distribution of y_{new} in this study is expressed as:

$$y_{\text{new}} \sim \mathcal{N}(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \beta, \lambda_\varepsilon^{-1} (1 + \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \mathbf{K}_u^{-1} \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}})). \quad (13)$$

We assume that a multilevel dataset $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$ and new explanatory variables \mathbf{x}_{new} , \mathbf{w}_{new} from an additional class are sampled from the population. The set of known data, \mathbf{D} , is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} := \{(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J), \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}, \mathbf{w}_{\text{new}}\}. \quad (14)$$

Based on Bayesian decision theory (James O. Berger 1985), we derive a prediction that minimizes the Bayes risk function, taking the squared error loss between the true new target variable y_{new} and the predicted variable \hat{y}_{new} from the new class. We refer to this prediction as the Bayes optimal prediction. The decision function δ in this study is defined as:

$$\delta : \mathbf{D} \mapsto \hat{y}_{\text{new}}. \quad (15)$$

The expected value of the squared error loss between y_{new} and $\delta(\mathbf{D})$ over the distribution of y_{new} , as specified in equation (13), is defined as the loss function $L(\cdot)$ and given by:

$$L(\delta(\mathbf{D}), \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon) = \int_{\mathcal{Y}} (y_{\text{new}} - \delta(\mathbf{D}))^2 p(y_{\text{new}} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon) dy_{\text{new}}. \quad (16)$$

Here, \mathcal{Y} denotes the set of possible values for y_{new} . The expected value of this loss function for the distribution of known data \mathbf{D} , as specified in equation (8), is called the risk function $R(\cdot)$ and expressed as:

$$R(\delta, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^J) = \int_{\mathcal{D}} L(\delta(\mathbf{D}), \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon) p(\mathbf{D} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) d\mathbf{D}. \quad (17)$$

Let $\mathbf{u}^J := \{\mathbf{u}_j | j = 1, \dots, J\}$, and \mathcal{D} denote the set of possible values for known data \mathbf{D} . The expected value of the risk function for the distribution of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε is defined as the Bayes risk function $\text{BR}(\cdot)$ and represented as:

$$\text{BR}(\delta) = \int_{\Theta} R(\delta, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J) p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \lambda_\varepsilon) p(\mathbf{u}^J | \lambda_\varepsilon) p(\lambda_\varepsilon) d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^J d\lambda_\varepsilon. \quad (18)$$

Here, Θ denotes the set of possible values for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε . The following corollary holds:

Corollary 3.1 *The prediction $\delta^*(\mathbf{D})$ that minimizes the Bayes risk function $\text{BR}(\delta)$ is given by:*

$$\delta^*(\mathbf{D}) = \int_{\mathcal{Y}} y_{\text{new}} p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D}) dy_{\text{new}}. \quad (19)$$

Here, the predictive distribution $p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D})$ is defined as:

$$p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D}) = \int_{\Theta} p(y_{\text{new}} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon) p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon | \mathbf{D}) d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^J d\lambda_\varepsilon. \quad (20)$$

The prediction $\delta^*(\mathbf{D})$ obtained from equations (19) and (20) is the Bayes optimal prediction.

4. Bayes Sub-optimal Prediction

Although the Bayes optimal prediction can be obtained from equations (19) and (20), analytically calculating the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon | \mathbf{D})$ is challenging. In this section, we approximate the posterior distribution using variational Bayes and compute an approximate solution to equation (19) following (Christopher M. Bishop 2006).

4.1 Approximate Posterior Distribution

In this study, we assume the following factorization for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε :

$$q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) = q(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \lambda_\varepsilon) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q(\mathbf{u}_j | \lambda_\varepsilon) \right) q(\lambda_\varepsilon). \quad (21)$$

Under this factorization, we seek the approximate posterior distribution $q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)$ that minimizes the Kullback-Leibler divergence to the true posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon | \mathbf{D})$, given by:

$$q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) = \arg \min_{q \in \Omega} \int_{\Theta} q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) \ln \frac{q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)}{p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon | \mathbf{D})} d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^J d\lambda_\varepsilon. \quad (22)$$

Here, Ω denotes the set of distributions $q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)$ that satisfy:

$$\Omega = \left\{ q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) \mid q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) = q(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q(\mathbf{u}_j \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) \right) q(\lambda_\varepsilon) \right\}. \quad (23)$$

For each component of the approximate posterior distribution for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε , the following relationships hold (Christopher M. Bishop 2006):

$$\ln q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = E_{q^*(\mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})], \quad (24)$$

$$\ln q^*(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = E_{q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})], \quad (25)$$

$$\ln q^*(\lambda_\varepsilon) = E_{q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) q^*(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})]. \quad (26)$$

By updating each of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε based on equations (24)–(26), we obtain an approximate solution. In this study, we update these parameters sequentially in the order of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε , where $q^{(t)}(\star)$ denotes the approximate posterior distribution of parameter \star at the t -th iteration.

4.1.1 Update of $q(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon)$

Equation (24) can be rewritten as:

$$\ln q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = E_{q^*(\mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\mathbf{D} \mid \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)] + E_{q^*(\lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon)] + \text{const.} \quad (27)$$

Thus, the update rule for $q(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ based on equation (27) is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = \mathcal{N}\left(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_\beta^{(t+1)})^{-1}\right). \quad (28)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)}$ and $\mathbf{K}_\beta^{(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{K}_\beta^{(t+1)} = \sum_{j=1}^J \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j + \mathbf{K}_\beta, \quad (29)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{K}_\beta^{(t+1)^{-1}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^J \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top (\mathbf{y}_j - \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t)}) + \mathbf{K}_\beta \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta \right). \quad (30)$$

4.1.2 Update of $q(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon)$

Equation (25) is rewritten as:

$$\ln q^*(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = E_{q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\mathbf{D} \mid \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)] \quad (31)$$

$$+ E_{q^*(\lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon; \mathbf{K}_u)] + \text{const.} \quad (32)$$

Thus, the update rule for $q(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon)$ based on equation (31) is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\mathbf{u}^J \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) = \prod_{j=1}^J \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{u}_j \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(t+1)})^{-1}\right). \quad (33)$$

Here, $\mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(t+1)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(t+1)} = \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j + \mathbf{K}_u, \quad (34)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(t+1)^{-1}} \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top (\mathbf{y}_j - \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)}) \quad (j = 1, \dots, J). \quad (35)$$

4.1.3 Update of $q(\lambda_\varepsilon)$

Equation (26) is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln q^*(\lambda_\varepsilon) &= E_{q^*(\beta|\lambda_\varepsilon)q^*(\mathbf{u}^J|\lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\mathbf{D} | \beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)] + E_{q^*(\beta|\lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\beta | \lambda_\varepsilon)] \\ &\quad + E_{q^*(\mathbf{u}^J|\lambda_\varepsilon)}[\ln p(\mathbf{u}^J | \lambda_\varepsilon; \mathbf{K}_u)] + \ln p(\lambda_\varepsilon) + \text{const..} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Thus, the update rule for $q(\lambda_\varepsilon)$ based on equation (36) is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\lambda_\varepsilon) = \text{Gam}\left(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid a_\varepsilon^{(t+1)}, b_\varepsilon^{(t+1)}\right). \quad (37)$$

Here, $a_\varepsilon^{(t+1)}$ and $b_\varepsilon^{(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} a_\varepsilon^{(t+1)} &= a_\varepsilon + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^J n_j + (J + Q + 1)(P + 1) \right), \\ b_\varepsilon^{(t+1)} &= b_\varepsilon + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J \left((\mathbf{y}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)} - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)})^\top \right. \\ &\quad \left. (\mathbf{y}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)} - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)}) + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)\top} \mathbf{K}_u \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t+1)} \right) \\ &\quad + (\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta)^\top \mathbf{K}_\beta (\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(t+1)} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta). \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

4.1.4 Calculation of the Variational Lower Bound

To evaluate the convergence of the posterior updates, we use the variational lower bound (Christopher M. Bishop 2006). Given the factorization in equation (21), the approximate posterior distribution at the t -th iteration is given by:

$$q^{(t)}(\beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) = q^{(t)}(\beta | \lambda_\varepsilon) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q^{(t)}(\mathbf{u}_j | \lambda_\varepsilon) \right) q^{(t)}(\lambda_\varepsilon). \quad (40)$$

Therefore, the variational lower bound at the t -th iteration is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^{(t)}(\mathbf{K}_u) &:= \int_{\Theta} \int_{\Phi} q^{(t)}(\beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{D}, \beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)}{q^{(t)}(\beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)} d\boldsymbol{\theta} d\boldsymbol{\phi} \\ &= E[\ln p(\mathbf{D} | \beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)] + E[\ln p(\beta | \lambda_\varepsilon)] + \sum_{j=1}^J E[\ln p(\mathbf{u}_j | \lambda_\varepsilon; \mathbf{K}_u)] \\ &\quad + E[\ln p(\lambda_\varepsilon)] - E[\ln q^{(t)}(\beta | \lambda_\varepsilon)] - \sum_{j=1}^J E[\ln q^{(t)}(\mathbf{u}_j | \lambda_\varepsilon)] \\ &\quad - E[\ln q^{(t)}(\lambda_\varepsilon)]. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Here, all expectations in equation (41) are taken with respect to $q^{(t)}(\beta, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon)$. We judge the convergence of the variational parameter updates by calculating the variational lower bound at each iteration.

4.1.5 Update of Hyperparameter \mathbf{K}_u

The hyperparameter \mathbf{K}_u , which is assumed to be constant within the variational Bayes algorithm, can be updated by differentiating the variational lower bound $\mathcal{L}^{(t)}(\mathbf{K}_u)$ for \mathbf{K}_u .

The update rule for \mathbf{K}_u is given by (Nakahara et al. 2023):

$$\mathbf{K}_u^* = J \left(\sum_{j=1}^J \frac{a_\varepsilon^{(t)}}{b_\varepsilon^{(t)}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j}^{(t)\top} + \mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(t)-1} \right)^{-1}. \quad (42)$$

By substituting \mathbf{K}_u^* into equations (34) and (39), we can sequentially update $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , λ_ε , and \mathbf{K}_u .

4.2 Derivation of Bayes Sub-optimal Prediction

Let T denote the number of iterations required for the variational lower bound to meet the convergence criterion. At this point, the approximate posterior distribution can be expressed as follows, based on equation (40):

$$q^{(T)}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon) = q^{(T)}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q^{(T)}(\mathbf{u}_j \mid \lambda_\varepsilon) \right) q^{(T)}(\lambda_\varepsilon). \quad (43)$$

By substituting this into the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^J, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})$ in equation (20), we obtain the Bayes sub-optimal predictive distribution for the new response variable y_{new} :

$$p^*(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{D}) \approx \text{St}(y_{\text{new}} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}, \lambda_{\text{new}}, \gamma_{\text{new}}). \quad (44)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}$, λ_{new} , and γ_{new} are given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(T)}, \quad (45)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{new}} = \left(1 + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \mathbf{K}_\beta^{(T)-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}} + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \mathbf{K}_u^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}} \right) \frac{a_\varepsilon^{(T)}}{b_\varepsilon^{(T)}}, \quad (46)$$

$$\gamma_{\text{new}} = 2a_\varepsilon^{(T)}. \quad (47)$$

Using this approximate distribution of the Bayesian optimal predictive distribution, we obtain the Bayes sub-optimal decision as follows:

$$\delta^*(\mathbf{D}) \approx \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta^{(T)}. \quad (48)$$

5. Experiments with Synthetic Data

In this section, we conduct two experiments using synthetic data. In Experiment 1, we compare the Bayes sub-optimal prediction derived in Section 4 with the prediction made by conventional methods that estimate parameters to predict the target variable. The aim is to confirm that our proposed method, which minimizes the Bayesian risk for prediction error of the target variable, achieves higher prediction accuracy than conventional methods. For this experiment, we compare prediction methods based on parameter estimation using REML and ML (Harvey Goldstein 2010) and predictions obtained through MCMC under the assumption of a conjugate prior distribution (Gelman & Hill 2006, Gelman 2013). Parameter estimation methods using REML and ML assume that parameters in the multilevel model are unknown fixed values. In Experiment 2, we compare the prediction accuracy between conventional methods and our proposed method using risk functions. Both experiments employ two sampling methods in order to validate our approach comprehensively.

- Sampling Method 1: Fixing the class sample size J while increasing the individual sample size n_j for each $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$.
- Sampling Method 2: Fixing the individual sample size n_j for each class while increasing the class sample size J .

5.1 Experiment 1 (Bayes Risk function)

In Experiment 1, data is generated following the steps below to compute the Bayes risk function. For simplicity, we set $P = 1$ and $Q = 1$.

- (i) Generate \mathbf{x}_{jk} and \mathbf{w}_j ($j = 1, \dots, J; k = 1, \dots, n_j$) from the standard normal distribution $N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.
- (ii) Fix $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta$, \mathbf{K}_β , \mathbf{K}_u , a_ε , and b_ε .
- (iii) Generate $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε .
- (iv) Generate the target variable y_{jk} ($j = 1, \dots, J; k = 1, \dots, n_j$).
- (v) Sample multilevel data $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$ from the population via class and individual sampling.
- (vi) Sample an individual with new explanatory variables \mathbf{x}_{new} and \mathbf{w}_{new} , perform prediction, and calculate the Bayes risk function.
- (vii) Repeat Step (vi) 500 times.
- (viii) Vary the sample size and repeat Steps (v)–(vii).
- (ix) Repeat Steps (iv)–(viii) 40 times.
- (x) Repeat Steps (iii)–(viii) 5 times.

The constants are set as $a_\varepsilon = 30$, $b_\varepsilon = 30$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta = (-20, -6.7, 6.7, 20)^\top$, $\mathbf{K}_\beta = 4\mathbf{I}$, and $\mathbf{K}_u = 2\mathbf{I}$.

5.1.1 Sampling Method 1 (Bayes Risk function)

In Sampling Method 1, the class sample size is set to $J = 6$, while the individual sample size varies as $n_j = 5, 16, \dots, 60$. The approximate Bayes risk function under Experiment 1 and Sampling Method 1 conditions is shown in Figure 1.

5.1.2 Sampling Method 2 (Bayes Risk function)

In Sampling Method 2, the class sample size varies as $J = 3, 10, \dots, 25$, while the individual sample size is fixed at $n_j = 15$. The approximate Bayes risk function computed similarly to Sampling Method 1 is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Approximate Bayes risk function (mean squared error of prediction)

Figure 2: Approximate Bayes risk function (mean squared error of prediction)

5.2 Experiment 2 (Risk Function)

In Experiment 2, data is generated following the steps below to compute the risk function.

- (i) Generate \mathbf{x}_{jk} and \mathbf{w}_j ($j = 1, \dots, J; k = 1, \dots, n_j$) from the standard normal distribution $N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.
- (ii) Fix $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_u$, and σ_ε^2 .
- (iii) Generate \mathbf{u}^J .
- (iv) Generate the target variable y_{jk} ($j = 1, \dots, J; k = 1, \dots, n_j$).
- (v) Sample multilevel data $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$ from the population via class and individual sampling.
- (vi) Sample an individual with new explanatory variables \mathbf{x}_{new} and \mathbf{w}_{new} , perform prediction, and calculate the risk function.
- (vii) Repeat Step (vi) 500 times.
- (viii) Vary the sample size and repeat Steps (v)–(vii).
- (ix) Repeat Steps (iii)–(viii) 400 times.

5.2.1 Sampling Method 1 (Risk Function)

In Sampling Method 1, the class sample size is set to $J = 15$, and the individual sample size varies as $n_j = 10, 20, \dots, 60$. For this experiment, constants are set as follows: $P = 9$, $Q = 6$, $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (-20, \dots, 20)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{70}$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_u = 0.05\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 7}$, and $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 = 0.2$. The approximate risk function under Sampling Method 1 is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Approximate risk function (mean squared error of prediction)

5.2.2 Sampling Method 2 (Risk Function)

In Sampling Method 2, the class sample size varies as $J = 5, 10, \dots, 30$, while the individual sample size is fixed at $n_j = 30$. Constants are set as $P = 7$, $Q = 4$, $\beta = (-20, \dots, 20)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{40}$, $\Sigma_u = 0.05\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 5}$, and $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 = 0.2$. The approximate risk function under Sampling Method 2 is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Approximate risk function (mean squared error of prediction)

5.3 Discussion

In this section, we discuss the results of Experiments 1 and 2. First, the results of Experiment 1 show that, for both Sampling Methods 1 and 2, our proposed prediction method achieves the minimum Bayes risk function compared to conventional methods, confirming that the variational Bayes sub-optimal prediction derived in Section 4 closely approximates the Bayesian optimal prediction derived in equation (19).

Next, regarding Experiment 2, data was generated based on the parameters assumed in equation (8), as proposed by Raudenbush & Bryk (2002) and Harvey Goldstein (2010). Figure 3 shows that for Sampling Method 1, the risk function of our proposed prediction method is smaller than that of REML and ML when the sample size is small. Moreover, Figures 3 and 4 indicate that our method’s risk function is almost equal to that of REML and ML for both Sampling Methods 1 and 2 for large sample sizes.

In both Experiments 1 and 2, it is evident that Sampling Method 2, which increases the class sample size, contributes more effectively to reducing Bayes risk function and the risk function than Sampling Method 1, which increases the individual sample size within each class.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we proposed a framework to derive a prediction that minimizes the Bayes risk function for predicting the response variable associated with newly sampled explanatory variables from a class not included in the known set of classes, based on Bayesian decision theory (James O. Berger 1985). Unlike conventional methods, this approach introduces

a prior distribution configuration that allows analytical derivation of the predictive distribution. We then derived a Bayes sub-optimal prediction by obtaining an approximate posterior distribution via variational Bayesian methods. Numerical experiments confirmed that, for both sampling strategies, the proposed method achieves a lower Bayes risk function than conventional methods relying on parameter estimation, yielding optimal predictions.

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